

TriLingual Slang & Idioms Dictionary:

English, Japanese & Korean

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Introduction

This dictionary is designed for learning modern loanwords and slang in English, Japanese and Korean. It contains popular expressions used in media, internet and everyday speech. It will be useful for those who are interested in the languages and cultures of Korean, Japanese and English, studying K-pop, J-pop, dramas and current communication trends.

Each word or expression is provided with an explanation and, where possible, examples of usage.

I hope that this dictionary will be a useful tool for those who are passionate about languages and want to get a better understanding of slang, expressions used in real life, media and internet.

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Slang

English	한국어(Korean)	日本語(Japanese)	Meaning
Chill	릴랙스하다 / 쿨하다 / 무던하다	リラックスする / 大らかな / ダラダラ	a state of relaxation, calmness.
Vibe	바이브 / 분위기	バイブ / 雰囲気	feeling or energy of a place or person.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This café has such a chill vibe. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 이 카페 분위기/바이브 진짜 릴랙스하다. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> このカフェの雰囲気/バイブはすごくリラックスする。 	
Bummer	실망	がっかり / いやなこと	a situation or event that is disappointing, or unpleasant.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> That new movie was a bummer! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 이 새로운 영화, 정말 실망이야! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> あの新しい映画はがっかりかった。 	
Dude / bro / man	놈 / 녀석/ 형 / 브로	ドゥード / ヤツ / 相棒	used for a casual conversation between friends.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hey dude whassup? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 야, 브로, 오늘 뭐 해? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ヨー、ドゥード！元気？ 	
Flex	플렉스	フレクス/ドヤる	show off or flaunt wealth or possessions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> He tried to impress me by flexing his huge muscles. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그는 큰 근육을 플렉스하면서 나에게 잘 보이려고 했어. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 彼は大きな筋肉をドヤりながら私にアピールしようとした。 	
Holy Moly	홀리몰리	やばい/なんてこった/すごい	express surprise or shock, like "OMG," "No way!"

G.O.A.T.	고트/최고	史上最高	"Greatest of All Time", used to describe someone or something as the best ever.
Iced coffee loyalist	얼죽아	ぬほど寒くてもアイス アメリカノ など冷たい飲料を飲むこと/ 真冬でもアイス派	Short for 얼어 죽어도 아이스 ("I'd rather freeze to death than not drink iced drinks")
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Even in freezing weather, he's an iced coffee loyalist. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 얼어 죽을 것 같은 날씨에도 그는 얼죽아야. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 凍えるような寒さでも、彼は真冬でもアイス派だね。 	
Never give up	중꺾마	大切なのは折れない心	Short for "중요한 것은 꺾이지 않는 마음" ("The important thing is an unbreakable will")
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> He has a never give up attitude. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그는 항상 중꺾마 정신이야. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 彼はいつも大切なのは折れない心という態度だ。 	
Fake hype	억텐	強引テンション	Short for "억지 텐션", meaning forced enthusiasm or exaggerated excitement.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> sometimes, his excitement feels like fake hype 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 가끔 그의 흥분은 억텐처럼 느껴져. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 時々彼のテンションは強引テンションみたいに感じる。 	
Is this for real?	이왜진	これマジ?	Short for "이게 왜진짜야?" ("Why is this real?")

Illiterate/Noob	까막눈	文盲 (もんもう)/ド素人 (どしろうと)	in a casual or joking sense, referring to someone inexperienced in something.
That 3 AM regret/Kicking the blanket in shame/Cringe moment	이불킥	黒歴史を思い出して悶える / 布団キック / イブルキク	"Blanket kick" – Korean slang for cringing at embarrassing memories, often at night.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ah... I tripped while confessing yesterday. I'm definitely gonna kick my blanket tonight. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 아... 어제 고백하다가 넘어졌어. 오늘 밤에 이불킥각. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> また黒歴史思い出して布団蹴りするわ... 	
Totally agree	킹정	認める/完全に同意する	Kingjeong" (킹정) is a Korean slang term combining "King" (킹) and "Injeong" (인정, meaning recognition or acknowledgment).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> That statement is so true! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그 말은 너무 킹정이지! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> その言葉、本当に認めざるを得ないね! 	
Red flag	깡다	レッドフラグ/人のやばい行動	A red flag is a sign that indicates you should be wary or cautious of someone or something
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If my dog doesn't like you, it's a red flag for me 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 우리 강아지가 너를 안 좋아하면, 그건 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> うちの犬があなたを嫌がったら、それは人のやばい行動のサイン/レッドフラグだよ。 	

	나한테 깬다 신호야		
Slay	짖었다	スレイ/イケてるね/完璧 だったね	an exclamation of encouragement that means to achieve something impressive or to succeed in something amazing. This is very similar to “killed it” and “nailed it”.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Damn, you have slayed that shot! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 와, 너 진짜 슛 짖었다. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> うわー！すごい完璧なシュートだったね！ 	
Cringe	오그라	引く/痛い	often used to describe something or someone that is embarrassing or awkward.
Pickme	남미새	ピック ミー	Term for a person, usually a young woman, seen as behaving in a contemptible way for attention and approval, usually from male peers.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> She’s a total pick me. She keeps dissing other girls in front of guys just to make herself look better 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 개는 완전 남미새야. 남자들 앞에서 다른 여자들을 깬아내리면서 자기만 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 彼女って完全にピックミー。男の前で他の女の子をディスって、自分を良く見せようとしてばかり 	

	돈보이려고 하잖아.		
Boss KFC	파오후	パオパオ/デブ社長	an insulting reference that suggests that a person is overweight. And it is connected with the fact that regular consumption of fast food leads to obesity.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> That person is called Boss KFC. I mean, he's super fat and only eats fried chicken. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그 사람은 파오후 라고 불러. 완전 똥똥하고 맨날 후라이드 치킨만 먹거든. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> あの人、パオパオって呼ばれてるよ。だってめっちゃデブで、フライドチキンばかり食ってるから。 	
Fr=for real/mood	팩폭	あるある	describing a mood or feeling appropriate to the context or situation. Used to emphasise the sincerity or seriousness of what is being said
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Studying an hour before an exam? Mood. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 시험 한 시간 전에 공부 시작하는 거, 팩폭이네. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 試験の1時間前に勉強し始めるの、あるあるすぎる。 	
Gold digger	속물/김치녀	玉の輿狙い	refers to an individual who exploits another person, typically a romantic partner, for their wealth or

			material possessions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • She only dates rich guys. Such a gold digger 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 그녀는 돈 보고 연애해. 완전 속물이야. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 彼女、金持ちしか狙わない。まさに玉の輿狙いだね。 	
Jackpot	개이득	超お得	slangy way of saying someone got a lot of benefit or something good happened to them.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I found my favorite sneakers on sale for 70% off. Jackpot! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 이번 할인 행사에서 원하는 물건을 반값에 샀어. 진짜 개이득이네! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • このセールでずっと欲しかったコートが半額で買えた！超お得だね！ 	
Noun+lover/preson	명사+덕후	名詞+派 (は)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cat person/lover 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 고양이덕후 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 猫派 	
Self-inflicted disaster	스불재	自業自得	(스스로 불러온 재앙) –Short for "a self-inflicted disaster," referring to a situation where someone creates their own problem.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • He ignored all the advice and ruined everything. That's pure self-inflicted disaster. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 그는 조언을 무시하고 결국 망쳤어. 완전 스불재. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 彼はアドバイスを無視して、すべてを台無しにした。完全に自業自得。 	
Like, Subscribe, Turn on Notifications	좋구알	高評価、チャンネル登録、通知オン	(좋아요 구독 알림설정) is short

			for 'Like, subscribe, turn on notifications,' a popular expression among youtubers and streamers in Korea
It's my style/type	완내스	私のスタイルだよ	abbreviation of '완전 내 스타일'. It means 'perfectly my type'
Plot twist!	반전	どんでん返し!	It refers to a surprising turn of events in stories or situations.
LOL/Lmao	ㅋㅋㅋ/ㅎㅎㅎ	笑 = www = 草	www comes from 笑 (warai, "laugh"), similar to "LOL." 草 (kusa, "grass") comes from www, since repeating "w" looks like grass.
Exactly! / So true! / fr	ㄹㅇ / 찐	それな	strong agreement with someone.
Favorite idol/Bias	최애	推し	Comes from 押す (osu, "to support or push") and refers to a favorite idol, celebrity, anime character, or public figure.
Idk tho	아닌가?/ 그런가?	知らんけど	express uncertainty, or add humor. It's similar to saying "Just saying..." or "But I'm not sure."
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I heard this movie is good. Idk tho. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 이 영화 재밌다던데? 모르겠는데? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> この映画、面白いらしいよ。知らんけど。 	

Mentally unstable person / Emo/ Depressed	멘헤라	メンヘラ	Derived from "mental health", originally referring to people with mental health issues
Ok/ k / aight	ㅇㅋ (오케이) / ㅇㅇ (응응)	りよ / り	short slang for 了解 (りょうかい, ryoukai), meaning "Got it"
Nice work! / GG	수고요	おつ	short for お疲れ様, meaning "Good job"
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nice work today! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 오늘도 일하느라 수고요! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 今日も仕事おつです! 	
Go viral	화제 났다	バズる	バズる (bazuru) – Japanese slang derived from buzz. Used for trending posts, videos, or topics gaining rapid attention.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This news went viral! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 이 뉴스 화제 났다! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> このニュース、バズってる! 	
Just Google it, silly.	구글에 검색해봐/구글 좀 해라, 병신아	ググれカス	Japanese internet slang meaning "Google yourself, silly."
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What's that? → Just Google it, silly. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그게 뭐야? → 구글 좀 해라, 병신아. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> それって何? → ググれカス。 	
Precious / wholesome / Pure	소중해/귀엽다	てえてえ	slang version of 尊い-とうとい meaning "precious," or

			"deeply emotional." It's often used by fans to express admiration for heartwarming or touching moments, like friendships, idols, or cute interactions.
Era	에라	エラ	Being obsessed with something or deeply into a trend.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I am in the gaming Era right now. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 요즘 게임 에라야. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 最近ゲームのエラに入っているよ 	
Fell off	페일 오프	フェル・オフ	Losing relevance, declining in performance, or no longer being as good as before.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> That singer fell off after their first album. (That singer isn't as popular after their first album.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그 가수 첫 앨범 이후로 페일 오프 했어. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> あの歌手、最初のアルバムの後フェル・オフしちゃったね。 	
Gatekeep	게이트키퍼	ゲートキープ	Keeping information or trends exclusive to a certain group, not sharing with outsiders.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stop gatekeeping that fashion brand! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그 브랜드 게이트키퍼 하지 마! 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> そのブランド、ゲートキープしないで教えてよ! 	
Bad take	배드 테이크	バッド・テイク	A bad opinion, a cringe-worthy or poorly thought-out statement.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> That was such a bad take on that movie. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 그 영화 리뷰 완전 배드 테이크야. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> その映画のレビュー、バッド・テイクだったね。 	
Hardcore fangirl/fanboy	빠순이 / 빠돌이	ガチオタ	Used to describe overly enthusiastic fans, often in K-pop fandoms.
No manners / Rude brat	싸가지	礼儀知らず	Describes someone who is rude or lacks social etiquette.
No-makeup face / Bare face	생얼	すっぴん	Refers to someone's natural face without any makeup.
Lucky Victory	럭키비키	ラッキー勝利	(럭키 + 빅토리) = Lucky + Victory. Used when someone wins something by luck rather than skill. Similar to "fluke win" or "getting lucky in a competition."

Idioms

English	한국어(Korean)	日本語(Japanese)	Meaning
A piece of cake / Easy as pie	누워서 떡 먹기 (Like eating rice cakes while lying down)	朝飯前(Before breakfast)	Something very easy to do
Hold someone back	발목을 잡다 (Hold someone's ankle)	足をひっぱる (Pull someone's leg)	To hinder someone's success

Slack off	농땡이 치다	油を売る (Sell oil)	Waste time instead of working
To be breathless	숨이 막히다	息をのむ (Drink one's breath)	To be shocked
Get along well	손발이 맞다 (Be in sync)	馬が合う (The horses match)	To be a good match with someone
To have a loose tongue	입이 가볍다 (Loose-lipped)	口が軽い (The mouth is light)	To be bad at keeping secrets
To be tight-lipped	입이 닳다	口がすっぱくなる (The mouth becomes sour)	To be good at keeping secrets
To say smth repeatedly	입이 무겁다	口が堅い (The mouth is tight)	To repeat something over and over
Want to sink into the floor/ Turn red as a beet	얼굴이 화끈거리다	顔から火が出る (Fire comes out from the face)	To be extremely embarrassed (Blush with embarrassment)
To eagerly wait for something	목이 빠지다	首を長くする (Make one's neck long)	To anticipate something impatiently
To flatter someone	아부를 떨다	ごまをする (Grind sesame)	To suck up to someone for favor
To take the long view	길게 보다	長い目で見る (Look with long eyes)	To be patient
To be extremely busy	고양이 손이라도 빌리고 싶다	猫の手も借りたい (Want to borrow even a cat's hand)	Busy
To be distant	서먹서먹하다	水臭い (Smells like water)	To be reserved or cold toward someone
So delicious that your cheeks falls	입에서 살살 녹다 / 뺨이 떨어 지다	ほおが落ちる (The cheeks fall)	Very tasty

To be in vain	수포로 돌아가다 / 물거품이 되다	水の泡になる (Become bubbles of water)	Efforts or achievements come to nothing
Have sharp ears / Be quick to catch news	귀가 밝다	耳が早い	Someone who is quick to catch on to rumors or news before others.
Want something so badly you can taste it	목구멍에서 손이 나오겠다	のどから手が出る	To desperately want something, like you're reaching for it from deep inside.
Building castles in the air	뜬구름을 잡다 (Grabbing passing clouds)	雲をつかむよう	Chasing unrealistic dreams or ideas.
Looking for a needle in a haystack	서울 가서 김 서방 찾는다 (Going to Seoul to find Mr. Kim)	東京で田中さんを探す	Searching for something nearly impossible to find.
A word once spoken cannot be taken back	발 없는 말이 천리 간다 (Words travel a thousand miles without feet)	悪事千里を走る	News and rumors spread quickly.
It takes two to tango	두 손뼉이 맞아야 소리가 난다 (It takes two hands to make a sound)	喧嘩両成敗	Conflict or success requires the involvement of both parties.
A hungry man is an angry man	금강산도 식후경 (Even the beautiful Geumgangsan is best enjoyed after a meal)	花より団子	Basic needs like food should be met before enjoying other things.
Small but mighty	작은 고추가 맵다 (A small pepper is spicy)	山椒は小粒でもぴりりと辛い	Small people or things can have great power.

Waiting eagerly	눈이 빠지도록 기다리다 (Waiting until your eyes pop out)	首を長くして待つ	Waiting for something with great anticipation.
The rich get richer	돈이 돈을 번다 (Money makes more money)	金は金を生む	Wealth tends to accumulate more wealth.
Birds of a feather flock together	가재는 게 편이라 (A crayfish sides with a crab)	類は友を呼ぶ	People tend to associate with those similar to them.
A pie in the sky	그림의 떡 (A rice cake in a picture)	絵に描いた餅	Something desirable but unattainable.
Don't count your chickens before they hatch	김치국부터 마시지 말라 (Don't drink kimchi soup first)	取らぬ狸の皮算用	Don't get ahead of yourself with expectations.
From rags to riches	개천에서 용 난다 (A dragon emerges from a small stream)	立身出世	A great person can come from humble beginnings.
Walls have ears	낮말은 새가 듣고 밤말은 쥐가 듣는다 (Daytime words are heard by birds, nighttime words are heard by mice)	壁に耳あり障子に目あり	Be careful what you say, as someone may be listening.
Rome wasn't built in a day	천리길도 한걸음부터 (A thousand-li journey starts with one step)	千里の道も一歩から	Every great achievement starts with small efforts.
You reap what you sow	콩심은데 콩나고 팥심은데 팥난다 (Plant beans, get beans; plant red beans, get red beans)	因果応報	Your actions determine your results.
A thorn in one's side	눈에 가시다 (Like a thorn in the eye)	目の上のたんこぶ	Something or someone constantly annoying or troublesome.

As small as a peanut	쥐꼬리 만큼 (As small as a mouse's tail)	雀の涙	A tiny amount, often of money or resources.
What goes around, comes around	가는 말이 고와야 오는 말이 곱다 (If you say kind words, kind words will return)	情けは人のためならず	Treat others well if you want to be treated well in return.
A fish rots from the head down	윗물이 맑아야 아랫물도 맑다 (If the upper stream is clean, the lower stream will be clean too)	上に立つ者が正しければ下も正しくなる	Leadership influences the entire group.
Practice makes perfect	서당개 삼 년에 풍월 읊는다 (A village dog recites poetry after three years)	門前の小僧習わぬ経を読む	Anyone can learn through experience and exposure.
To Bite the Bullet	이를 악물다	苦い薬も飲まねばならぬ	Forcing yourself to do something unpleasant or difficult, or being brave in a tough situation.
Kill Two Birds With One Stone	일석이조	一石二鳥	Achieve two things with one action
Let the Cat Out of the Bag	비밀이 새다	馬脚を現す	Accidentally reveal a secret.
Don't Put All Your Eggs in One Basket	모든 것을 한곳에 걸지 마라	一つの籠にすべての卵を入れるな	Avoid concentrating all resources in one area to reduce risk.
Once in a Blue Moon	하늘의 별 따기	滅多にない	Something that happens very rarely.
Burn the Midnight Oil	밤을 새워 공부하다	夜を徹して働く	Work late into the night
Burn the Candle at Both Ends	몸을 혹사하다	体を酷使する	Exhaust oneself by working too hard.

At the Drop of a Hat	즉각적으로	即座に	Do something immediately without hesitation.
Cry Over Spilt Milk	엎질러진 물이다	覆水盆に返らず	Waste time being upset over something that can't be changed.
You Can't Judge a Book by its Cover	겉만 보고 판단하지 마라	外見で判断するな	Don't judge people or things based on appearance.
Don't Count Your Chickens Before They Hatch	김치국부터 마시지 마라	捕らぬ狸の皮算用	Don't assume success before it happens.
Go the Extra Mile	한 발 더 나아가다	一層の努力をする	Put in more effort than expected.
Raining Cats and Dogs	비가 억수같이 내리다	土砂降りの雨	Raining heavily.
Throw in the Towel	포기하다	白旗を上げる	Give up or admit defeat.
Cross That Bridge When You Come To It	그때 가서 생각하다	その時が来たら考える	Deal with a problem when it arises.
When in Rome, Do as the Romans Do	로마에 가면 로마법을 따르라	郷に入れば郷に従え	Adapt to local customs.